

1 **Boron-doped diamond synthesized by chemical vapor deposition as a**
2 **heating element in a multi-anvil apparatus**

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18 **Abstract:**

19 We tested boron doped diamond (BDD) synthesized by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) as
20 a heating element in a multi-anvil apparatus. We succeeded in manufacturing BDD into a
21 tubular shape by laser cutting and electric discharging machining. The BDD tube shaped by
22 the electric discharging machining was contaminated by discharging electrode materials (Mo
23 and W), which affected the heating performance. The laser-cut BDD tube has a clean surface,
24 and therefore had a good heating performance. We succeeded in generating temperature as
25 high as 2670 K at a pressure around 30 GPa with laser-cut heater. Heating reproducibility
26 was confirmed through repeated heating and cooling cycles. The recovered sample shows
27 that a higher temperature generation above 2670 K was prevented by eutectic melting of
28 ZrO_2 thermal insulator and Al_2O_3 sample. Owing to the commercial availability with a
29 reasonable price, CVD-BDD heaters are more practical than a high-pressure synthesized
30 BDD heaters for wide applications.

31 **Key words:** Chemical vapor deposition, Boron-doped diamond, Multi-anvil apparatus,
32 High temperature generation, X-ray transparency

33 I. Introduction

34 Multi-anvil apparatus (MAA) has a capability to generate lower mantle pressures (>23
35 GPa), and is an important tool to study physical and chemical properties of deep-Earth
36 materials [1]. Temperatures over 3000 K are vital for melting of mantle materials under lower-
37 mantle conditions [e.g. 2-5]. Because of the refractory and X-ray transparency, boron-doped
38 diamond (BDD) is a good heating material for ultrahigh-temperature generation using electrical
39 resistive heating in MAA [6] and diamond anvil cell [7]. It has recently drawn a special
40 attention after its successful temperature generation up to 4000 K [6] and application to
41 viscosity measurement of silicate melts at pressures to 30 GPa and temperatures to 3300 K in
42 MAA [8].

43 In these studies, significant efforts have been made to find the best form of BDD
44 (precursor or pre-synthesized BDD) for manufacturing furnaces [6, 9-12]. The stable
45 temperature generation up to 4000 K demonstrated overall advantage of pre-synthesis than in-
46 situ synthesis using a graphite-boron composite as a precursor [6]. In those studies, BDD tubes
47 were directly synthesized at high pressure or molded from powders, which was ground from
48 high-pressure synthesized BDD blocks [6,8]. These tremendous efforts and costs for
49 preparation limited its wide variety of applications. A convenient way to obtain BDD is thus
50 needed. Moreover, the assembly size dramatically decreases to generate higher pressures. For
51 experiments above 30 GPa, the edge lengths of octahedral pressure media are less than 7 mm
52 in the majority of studies, and small heaters accommodated in such small volumes should have
53 thin walls with thickness less than 0.2 mm. It is extremely difficult to prepare such thin BDD
54 tubes by direct synthesis or molding from powders. To obtain thin BDD tubes, direct shaping
55 from a BDD block is required.

56 The chemical vapor deposition (CVD) is currently a powerful industrial method to
57 synthesize diamond and BDD films. Recently, we found companies that produce and deal
58 CVD-BDD blocks with dimensions of $10 \times 10 \times 1.2 \text{ mm}^3$. These dimensions allow
59 manufacturing heaters for the smallest MAA assemblies. Therefore, it should be more practical
60 to purchase CVD-BDD blocks from company and manufacture heaters from them than to
61 synthesize BDD blocks by high-pressure experiments. In this study, we shaped CVD-BDD

62 blocks in tubular shapes by two methods, and tested their heating performance in MAA
63 assemblages.

64

65 **2. Materials and methods**

66 **A. Preparation of tubular CVD-BDD heater**

67 The CVD-BDD blocks used in this study had dimensions of $10 \times 10 \times 1.2 \text{ mm}^3$ (Figure 1a,d),
68 and were purchased from Changsha 3 Better Ultra-hard Materials Co., Ltd. in a price of ~65
69 Euro/piece. The product description of this item shows a boron content of 0.5 wt.%, which is
70 the highest boron content of BDD commercially provided by companies to the best of our
71 knowledge.

72 BDD tubes were manufactured by the following two methods.

73 As a heating element, BDD is electrically conductive. In the first method, manufacturing
74 was, therefore, made by the electric discharge machining (EDM). We used a micro electric
75 discharge machine system to manufacture BDD tubes. A tungsten rod with 0.6-mm diameter
76 was used as an electrode for boring an inner hole of a BDD tube and a molybdenum tube with
77 1.5-mm outer and 0.9-mm inner diameters as an electrode for manufacturing an outer surface
78 of the BDD tube. The discharging energy was set to be 20 μJ with a peak power of 0.8 W. The
79 machining process took around 3 days to produce one tube.

80 As the black color of BDD shown, BDD is a good absorber of visible light. BDD blocks
81 were therefore cut by a laser in the second method. The cutting was conducted by a company
82 (Dutch Diamond Technologies BV) using a green laser with a wavelength of 532 nm.
83 Production of 64 pieces costed around 1200 Euro.

84

85 **B. Characterization of CVD-BDD**

86 The BDD blocks and tubes were characterized by a micro-focused X-ray diffraction
87 (XRD) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Figure 1(b,e) show top and side views of a
88 BDD tube shaped by EDM. A BDD tube with dimensions of 0.9/0.6/1.2 mm was successfully
89 fabricated. However, the surface of BDD tube was contaminated by small amounts of Mo oxide
90 (Mo_4O_{11}) as shown by the micro-focused X-ray diffraction pattern (Figure 2). The inner wall
91 should also be contaminated by small amounts of W oxide although we were not able to check

92 it by X-ray diffraction due to experimental difficulty. We also tried to remove the Mo oxide by
93 rinsing the BDD tube in 10 wt.% HCl solution for more than 12 hours at ~ 100 °C. The X-ray
94 diffraction pattern (Figure 2) and SEM images (Figure 3 (c, d)), however, show that the Mo
95 oxide remained, which may limit high temperature generation of this heater (Table 1).

96 Figure 1 (c,f) show top and side views of a BDD tube with dimensions of 0.9/0.6/1.2 mm
97 manufactured by a laser. X-ray diffraction pattern (Figure 2) and SEM images (Figure 3 (e, f))
98 show that the surface of the BDD tube was clean without any contamination. Furthermore, we
99 emphasize that the laser cutting can produce a much larger number of BDD tubes than EDM.
100 We, therefore, conclude that the laser cutting is a better way than EDM. In this study, the
101 majority of high-pressure experiments were conducted using laser-cut BDD tubes.

102

103 **C. Heating tests at high pressures**

104 The heating tests were conducted at high pressure and temperature in a 6-axis multi-anvil
105 apparatus installed at Bayerisches Geoinstitut, University of Bayreuth [13]. Cell assemblies
106 were compressed to 30 GPa by using sintered-diamond cubes with a 1.5 mm truncated edge
107 length as second-stage anvils. After reaching a target press load (1.6 MN), heating was
108 performed by power control with voltage and current limits of 50V and 60A, respectively.
109 Temperatures were measured by a $W_{97}Re_3$ - $W_{75}Re_{25}$ thermocouple.

110

111 **3. Results and discussions**

112 **A. Heating performance of EDM-shaped BDD**

113 We first tested the EDM-shaped BDD tubular heater. Figure 4a shows a schematic view
114 of the cell assembly. An MgO octahedron with an edge length of 5.7 mm was used as a pressure
115 medium. The heating was terminated at ~ 1870 K when the heating became unstable. Some
116 metal droplets, containing W, Re and Mo, were found along the inner side of heater in the
117 recovered sample, which suggested melting of the thermocouple (Figure 4 (b, c)). Since the
118 melting temperature of W/Re alloy is much higher than 1870 K, the melting should have been
119 caused by the Mo and W oxides, which remained on the BDD tube surface after manufacturing.
120 Therefore, EDM is not an appropriate method to prepare BDD tubes for high-temperature
121 generation.

122 **B. Heating performance of laser-shaped BDD**

123 Next, we tested the laser-shaped BDD tubes. In some early runs, we found that
124 electromotive forces (thermocouple reading) were affected by the alternating voltages of the
125 heater, because the thermocouple contacted with the heater in the cell assembly shown in Figure
126 4a. To overcome this problem and ensure correctness of thermocouple reading, we designed a
127 new assembly, as shown in Figure 5 (a,b). The thermocouple was set parallel to the heater axis
128 and was insulated from the heater using an MgO or Al₂O₃ tube, which ensures that the
129 thermocouple is free from heater noise. In these tests, MgO octahedrons with an edge length
130 of 5.7 mm were used as pressure media. The edges and corners of the octahedrons were
131 truncated. The BDD tubular heaters were 1.2 or 1.6 mm in length. The 1.6 mm BDD tube was
132 made by connecting two 0.8 mm tubes, which were ground from 1.2 mm tubes. Mo was used
133 as electrodes.

134 Figure 6 shows the power-temperature and power-resistance relationships of run M772.
135 In the first heating, temperature was gradually increased to 2270 K at a rate of ~30 K/min, and
136 was kept for 20 minutes. The apparent resistance of the heater first decreased from 6 to ~0.9 Ω
137 until ~1270 K, then, almost remained constant or slightly increased (Figure 6b). This behavior
138 was similar to that of high-pressure synthesized BDD heaters [6]. To examine reproducibility
139 of power-temperature-resistance relations, we decreased temperature to 770 K and then
140 increased again. The power-temperature relationships show good reproducibility among the
141 first heating, first cooling and second heating paths. In the second heating, we attempted to
142 generate temperature as high as possible, and succeeded in generating 2670 K. The heating was,
143 then, terminated due to the fluctuation of heater resistance. The recovered sample showed an
144 eutectic melting among ZrO₂, Al₂O₃ and CaO (Figure 7), which should be a cause of the heater
145 resistance fluctuation. Therefore, CVD-BDD is useful for ultrahigh temperature generation at
146 high pressure. Considering its commercial availability with a reasonable price, a CVD-BDD
147 heater is more practical than a high-pressure synthesized BDD heater for wide applications.

148 **C. Remarks for ultra-high temperature generation in small cell**

149 Figure 8 shows power-temperature relationships with different cell assemblies. The
150 different heater lengths have only limited effects on the heating efficiency (Table 1 and Figure
151 8). The cell assemblies with ZrO₂ thermal insulators have much higher heating efficiencies than

152 those without ones. Based on our experience, heating powers should be kept below 800 W to
153 prevent the temperatures of the anvil's tops for electrodes from exceeding the eutectic melting
154 point of the Co-C system (~1600 K at ambient pressure). Therefore, increase of heating
155 efficiency is essential for ultrahigh-temperature generation.

156 There are two methods to increase the heating efficiency: thermal insulation and decrease
157 of heater diameters. Since the heaters diameters were already very small (0.6 mm in inner
158 diameter), the sample space was too limited to decrease the heater dimensions furthermore. It
159 will also be very difficult to assemble a cell when the heater dimensions were decreased.
160 Thermal insulation is therefore essential for ultrahigh-temperature generation in small cell
161 assemblies. Our traditional thermal insulator CaO-stabilized ZrO₂, however, is not suitable for
162 ultrahigh-temperature generation due to an eutectic melting among ZrO₂ and CaO. Moreover,
163 synchrotron X-ray is needed to determine pressure in small cell assemblies due to the low
164 reproducibility of pressure generation among different runs, which in turn requires an X-ray
165 transparent thermal insulator. The common X-ray transparent thermal insulator is boron epoxy.
166 However, it has been recognized many disadvantages of using boron-epoxy, such as limited
167 pressure range (practically <10 GPa), enhancing blow-out probability, and dehydrated water
168 from epoxy. Therefore, novel X-ray transparent thermal insulating material is desired. One
169 candidate is a recently developed boron-MgO composite [14].

170

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180 **REFERENCES**

181

182 [1] Ito, E., 2007. 2.08 Theory and practice-multi-anvil cells and high-pressure experimental
183 method. Mineral physics. In: Treatise on Geophysics, vol. 2, pp. 197-230.

184 [2] Zerr, A., Diegeler, A., Boehler, R., 1998. Solidus of Earth's deep mantle. *Science*,
185 281(5374), 243-246.

186 [3] Fiquet, G., Auzende, A. L., Siebert, J., Corgne, A., Bureau, H., Ozawa, H., Garbarino, G.,
187 2010. Melting of peridotite to 140 gigapascals. *Science*, 329(5998), 1516-1518.

188 [4] Nomura, R., Hirose, K., Uesugi, K., Ohishi, Y., Tsuchiyama, A., Miyake, A., Ueno, Y.,
189 2014. Low core-mantle boundary temperature inferred from the solidus of
190 pyrolite. *Science*, 343(6170), 522-525.

191 [5] Andrault, D., Bolfan-Casanova, N., Nigro, G. L., Bouhifd, M. A., Garbarino, G., Mezouar,
192 M., 2011. Solidus and liquidus profiles of chondritic mantle: Implication for melting of the
193 Earth across its history. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.*, 304(1-2), 251-259.

194 [6] Xie, L., Yoneda, A., Yoshino, T., Yamazaki, D., Tsujino, N., Higo, Y., Tange, Y., Irifune,
195 T., Shimei, T., Ito, E., 2017. Synthesis of boron-doped diamond and its application as a heating
196 material in a multi-anvil high-pressure apparatus. *Rev. Sci. Inst.*, 88, p.093904.

197 [7] Ozawa, H., Tateno, S., Xie, L., Nakajima, Y., Sakamoto, N., Kawaguchi, S.I., Yoneda, A.
198 and Hirao, N., Boron-doped diamond as a new heating element for internal-resistive heated
199 diamond-anvil cell. *High Press. Res.*, 38(2), 120-135.

200 [8] Xie, L., Yoneda, A., Yamazaki, D., Manthilake, G., Higo, Y., Tange, Y., Guignot, N., King,
201 A., Scheel, M. and Andrault, D., 2020. Formation of bridgmanite-enriched layer at the top
202 lower-mantle during magma ocean solidification. *Nat. Comm.*, 11(1), 1-10.

203 [9] Yamada, A., Irifune, T., Sumiya, H., Higo, Y., Inoue, T. and Funakoshi, K.I., 2008.
204 Exploratory study of the new B-doped diamond heater at high pressure and temperature and its
205 application to in situ XRD experiments on hydrous Mg-silicate melt. *High Press. Res.*, 28(3),
206 255-264.

207 [10] Shatskiy, A., Yamazaki, D., Morard, G., Cooray, T., Matsuzaki, T., Higo, Y., Funakoshi,
208 K.I., Sumiya, H., Ito, E. and Katsura, T., 2009. Boron-doped diamond heater and its application

209 to large-volume, high-pressure, and high-temperature experiments. *Rev. Sci. Inst.*, 80(2),
210 023907.

211 [11] Yoneda, A., Xie, L., Tsujino, N., Ito, E., 2014. Semiconductor diamond heater in the
212 Kawai multianvil apparatus: an innovation to generate the lower mantle geotherm. *High Press.*
213 *Res.*, 34(4), 392-403.

214 [12] Xie, L., Yoneda, A., Yoshino, T., Fei, H., Ito, E., 2016. Graphite–boron composite heater
215 in a Kawai-type apparatus: the inhibitory effect of boron oxide and countermeasures. *High*
216 *Press. Res.*, 36(2), 105-120.

217 [13] Manthilake, G., Walte, N., Frost, D. J., 2012. A new multi-anvil press employing six
218 independently acting 8 MN hydraulic rams. *High Press. Res.*, 32(2), 195-207.

219 [14] Xie, L., Yoneda, A., Xu, F., Higo, Y., Wang, C., Tange, Y., King, A., Antonangeli, D.,
220 Morard, G., Guignot, N., 2020. Boron-MgO composite as an X-ray transparent pressure
221 medium in the multi-anvil apparatus. *Rev. Sci. Inst.*, 91, 043903.

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224 TABLE 1. Summary of temperature generation at ~30 GPa using CVD-BDD heaters. The
 225 heater size is defined in the order of outer diameter, inner diameter, and length. The pressures
 226 were estimated based on a calibration curve using pressure fixed points of ZnS and GaP phase
 227 transitions and a constant thermal pressure of 2 MPa/K, which was estimated by another run
 228 using synchrotron X-ray (the results will be published elsewhere). The error of estimated
 229 pressure is ~3 GPa.

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Run #	Manufacturing	Heater size	Thermal insulator	sample	Highest Temperature /K
M714	EDM	0.9/0.6/1.2	None	MgO+10 wt. %diamond	1870
M760	Laser cutting	0.9/0.6/1.2	ZrO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃ tube	2170
M766	laser cutting	0.9/0.6/1.2	MgO	MgO tube	1970
M772	laser cutting	0.9/0.6/1.6	ZrO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃ tube +ZrO ₂ tube	2670
M773	laser cutting	0.9/0.6/1.6	ZrO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃ tube +ZrO ₂ tube	2270

231

232 **Figure**

233

234 Figure 1. Microscopic images of commercial CVD-BDD blocks and manufactured tubes. (a,d)
235 Top and side views of commercial CVD-BDD blocks, respectively. (b,e) Top and side views
236 of a 0.9/0.6/1.2 mm BDD tube made by EDM, respectively. (c,f) Top and side views of a
237 0.9/0.6/1.2 mm BDD tube manufactured by laser cutting, respectively.

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241 Figure 2. Micro focused X-ray diffraction patterns of a BDD block and tubes. X-ray beams
 242 with a wavelength of 1.79026 Å were focused to a 100×400 μm in diameter using an IFG
 243 polycapillary X-ray mini-lens. BDD block: the original BDD block used for cutting tubes.
 244 Laser cut BDD: BDD tube cut by laser cut method. EDM cut BDD: BDD tube cut by EDM.
 245 The HCl washed BDD tube was washed by 10 wt.% HCl for more than 12 hours. The arrows
 246 marking the small peaks, are not related to diamond or graphite. These peaks can be matched
 247 with none of Mo₂C, MoO₂, MoO₃, WC. They roughly match the peaks of Mo₄O₁₁.

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251 Figure 3. Backscattered electron images of the BDD block and tubes. (a,b) CVD-BDD block.

252 (c,d) the EDM-manufactured BDD tube after washing by HCl solution. The white part on the

253 tube is the contamination of Mo electrode. (e,f) the laser-cut BDD tube, the surface of which

254 is clean.

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256

257 Figure 4. Experiment using the EDM-manufactured BDD tube (Run M714). (a) A schematic

258 drawing of the cell assembly. A TiC tube was used as electrode. MgO with 10 wt% diamond

259 (Dia.) was used as sample. (b, c) Backscattered electron images of the recovered sample.

260 Compared with (a), the images (b) and (c) are rotated by ~90 degrees.

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265 Figure 5. Cell assemblies with laser-cut BDD heaters. The heater length was 1.2 and 1.6 for
 266 assembly (a) and (b), respectively. Assembly (a) was used for M760 and M766 in Table 1;
 267 assembly (b) was used for M772 and M773 in Table 1.

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271 Figure 6. Power–temperature (a) and power-resistance (b) diagrams of laser-cut BDD heater
272 (run M772).

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275 Figure 7. Optical microscopic image (a) and backscattered electron images (b, c, d) of
 276 recovered sample of run M772. (a) Optical image showing a wide view of the cell. (b)
 277 Backscattered electron image of overview of the heater inside. In order to get well polished
 278 sample, the diamond heater and cell assembly out of it was removed by diamond bits and
 279 sample was polished a $\sim 30\ \mu\text{m}$ deeper than (a). c, d rectangles mark the area of sample where
 280 image (c) and (d) were zoomed up, respectively. (c) Zoomed up backscattered electron image
 281 of rectangle c in (b). Al_2O_3 sample was not melted and grown from a grain size of $\sim 5\ \mu\text{m}$ to
 282 $\sim 30\ \mu\text{m}$. (d) Zoomed up backscattered electron image of rectangle d in (b). Dendritic texture
 283 was found, indicating eutectic melting between sample (Al_2O_3) and thermal insulator (CaO
 284 stabilized zirconia).

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288 Figure 8. Summary of power–temperature relationships of laser-cut BDD heaters.

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